

The Effect of Impinging WC-12Co Particles Temperature on Thickness of HVOF Thermally Sprayed Coatings

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Abstract : In this paper, the effect of WC-12Co particle Temperature in HVOF thermal spraying process on the coating thickness has been studied. The statistical results show that the spray distance and oxygen-to-fuel ratio are more effective factors on particle characterization and thickness of HVOF thermal spraying coatings. Spray Watch diagnostic system, scanning electron microscopy (SEM), X-ray diffraction and thickness measuring system were used for this purpose.

Keywords : HVOF, temperature thickness, velocity, WC-12Co

Conference Title : ICMME 2014 : International Conference on Mechanical and Materials Engineering

Conference Location : Melbourne, Australia

Conference Dates : December 11-12, 2014